

ISSUES OF ARTISTIC SKILL IN ENGLISH TRANSLATIONS OF UZBEK STORIES AND NARRATIVES OF 20TH CENTURY

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Abstract. In this article, the peculiarities of the direct translations of 20th century Uzbek short stories and narratives into English are studied. Among the Uzbek short stories created in the 20th century, Gafur Ghulam's short story "A Naughty Boy", which is translated by I.M. Tokhtasinov, U.R. Yoldoshev. "My Thief Boy" in English, which is translated Mahmuda Saydumarova, and critical comments about translated works are presented.

Keywords: Gafur Gulam, Abdulla Kahhor, "Naughty boy", translation, XX century, stories, narrative, artistic skills.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada XX asr o'zbek qissa va hikoyalarining ingliz tiliga bevosita tarjimalarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari o'rganilgan, XX asrda yaratilgan o'zbek qissa va hikoyalaridan G'afur G'ulomning "Shum bola" qissasi, asarning I.M.To'xtasinov, U.R.Yo'ldoshevning ingliz tilidagi "A Naughty Boy", "Mening o'g'rigina bolam" hikoyasi, asarning Mahmuda Saydumarova qilgan inglizcha "My Thief Boy" tarjimasi haqidagi ma'lumotlar tahlil qilingan, tarjima asarlar haqidagi tanqidiy mulohazalar bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: G'afur G'ulom, Abdulla Qahhor, "Shum bola", tarjima, XX asr, hikoyalar, qissalar, badiiy mahorat.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются особенности прямых переводов узбекских рассказов и повестей XX века на английский язык. Среди узбекских рассказов, созданных в XX веке, - рассказ Гафура Гулама "Непослушный мальчик", который перевели И.М. Тохтасинов, У.Р. Йолдошев. "Мой мальчик-воробей" на английском языке, который перевела Махмуда Сайдумарова, а также представлены критические замечания о переведенных произведениях.

Ключевые слова: Гафур Гулам, Абдулла Каххор, "Непослушный мальчик", перевод, XX век, рассказы, повествование, художественное мастерство.

Stories in Uzbek literature have significant role and importance. The development of short stories in Uzbek literature is associated with the names of Gafur Ghulam, Abdulla Qahhor, and Togay Murad. They made a significant contribution to the development of short stories in Uzbek literature through a series of short stories. Such works of art created in Uzbek literature served to enrich literary translation. Some of the stories created in Uzbek literature were translated by Mahmuda Saidumarova, and the collection was called "A Collection of Uzbek Short Stories". The collection also includes stories from the 20th century. The collection was published by the Author House publishing house in 2012. The collection also includes modern stories of the 20th century. The collection also includes modern stories of the 20th century. For example, Khairiddin Sultanov's "You are so sweet, you bitter life!" is a story, in which impressively describes how the hero of the fight against the Russian invaders, the leader of the resistance movement, the old woman was able to say goodbye to her son, who was captured and hanged by the invading troops led by the Russian general von Kaufman. From 1865 to 1880, Qurbonjon dodkhoh, the Queen of Oloy, gathered the nation around her, and with a single sword in her hand, fought against General Fon Kaufman. She was so courageous that when her son, Qamchibek, was held as a captive by Kaufman and was about to be hanged by his orders, she came to the gallows and

told her son, "Farewell, my son. Your father and grandfather have also martyred at the hands of their enemies; we have inherited martyrdom. I am satisfied with what I have fed you." Saying this, she turned around, climbed her horse, and without watching her son die in torture and pain, left.

In this part of the work, the national character of the Uzbek people is highly reflected. In the struggle for the Motherland, the character of our people is ready to go till the death.

Ghafur Ghulam's story "My Thief Boy" tells an impressive story of tragic events in the seventeenth years of the 20th century based on a simple story. The thief is not actually a thief, he is a poor man who, due to life difficulties, fell into this trap to feed his children. And the old woman is a weak woman who spends her nights worrying about the fate of her grandchildren whose parents have died. Two characters of the Uzbek people were shown in this place. First, it is the fact that Uzbek people love children, and secondly, it is the superiority of the spirit of humanism. If the old woman did not have humanism, she would not have treated the thief in such a sincere manner. The old woman here is not only a woman who showed mercy to a thief, but a typical representative of all Uzbek mothers.

In the first half of the 20th century, Abdullah Qahhor also wrote stories effectively. He received the name of "master of story writing" in literary studies for the stories he created during this period. Abdulla Qahhor's satirical stories created during this period are based on revealing laughter. Baqijon Baqoev in "Literature Teacher" is a satirical character who is subject to this type of laughter. Being a teacher of literature, Bagijon Baqoev, unable to answer his sister-in-law's simple questions, exposes himself in front of the reader by diverting the conversation in all directions in order to hide his illiteracy. One of the positive achievements of translation is that a wide path has been opened to the translation of works from the original rather than from the translation. In our opinion, translating the work using the translated text instead of the original creates a number of disadvantages for the translation:

1. If there are omitted texts in the previously translated text, this in turn will not be reflected in the next translation.
2. If the original content is mistranslated in the translation, this mistake will be repeated in the second translation.
3. Translating works not from the original text, but from the translation text will cause the creation of perfect translations of the work.

The term "artistic" refers to the method of depicting the reality and existence that a person perceives with the help of artistic symbols. This term has been used in Uzbek literary studies since the beginning of the 20th century. There are different definitions of "artistic". Literary scientist H. Umurov writes about "artistic" as follow: "Both the soul and blood of art is artistry". The scope of the concept of "artistic" includes a specific field of art, the goal set by the writer in the work of art, its clear expression, the fulfillment of the writer's intention and the creation of the work. The creator may not always have the opportunity to directly express the thought he wants to express, but he can express it by incorporating it into an artistic work. Among the Uzbek stories of the 20th century, such as "A naughty boy", "My thief boy", "A literature teacher", high examples of artistic image are expressed. We can see that in the story "Shum bola" it is highly reflected in the scenes dedicated to the image of a naughty boy, in the image of nature, as well as in the image of the rich man's portrait. In "Literature teacher", the sarcasm image given to the character of the literature teacher Baqijon Baqoyev is one of the parts of the work that require special analysis from the point

of view of artistry. We analyzed the works of art named above from the point of view of translation, language and literature, and the places where artistry and artistic skills are reflected.

Original: Pochcham bilan ammam bu gul, bu hayvonlarning har bittasini nuri diydalariday parvarish qiladilar. [6, 12]

Translation: My brother-in-law and my aunt liked them very much.

In this text, “nuridiydalariday” served as a means of creating artistry. This word is used for a child, but in this place it is not in the sense of a child, but in the sense that he respects animals as his children. In the translation, it is said that he loved it very much. In our opinion, it would be better if it was translated as “adored”. While recreating the means of artistic representation given in the original text, the translators tried to preserve the artistic features of the text.

An artist's style is made up of a number of tools and is not defined solely by language or artistic elements. When determining the style, we can cite the following aspects:

1. Philosophical views of the artist about life.
2. Realistic views on life.
3. The artist's ability to analyze life and the events taking place in it from a psychological point of view.
4. Awareness of the living language of people living in society, etc.

Different analysis and interpretation of life by the artist, in turn, directly affects the style of the work he creates. If someone expresses the tragedies that happened in life in a tragic way, another artist can depict them in a comic way and bring them into his work. For example, in Gafur Ghulam's story “My Thief boy”, the development of events is depicted in a realistic style. Philosophical observations take the leading place. It is of particular importance that the language of the works created by the artist is folk. Abdulla Qahhor also has his own style, which describes the current reality in a mostly satirical and humorous way. A. Qahhor's way of completing the work also shows its originality. In this sense, artistic language is not a norm. The artistic style is distinguished by the fact that it includes all the signs of style. Literally speaking, all the signs of style can be found in works of art.

The work done by the creator reaches representatives of other languages through translators. The extent to which the original is spread depends on the skill of the translator. Artistic skill is the unique artistic world of the writer, his artistry in creating an artistic text. The skill of the translator is manifested in the skillful presentation of the original language, the re-creation of images in the second language, the ability to find an alternative to the means of artistic representation, and so on. The skill of the translator is evident in the translation of the work of art. Because the translation of a work of the art is not an example of translating the information contained in one work into another language.

It is known that the writer's style means his unique way of describing in creating an artistic character. Each artist has his own individual style. Style defines the identity of the creator. But the style should not be considered as invented by the writer himself. From the translations of “A naughty boy”, “Literature Teacher”, “My Thief Boy” from the translations of 20th century Uzbek stories and short stories, which are the object of our research, we determined and analysed the extent to which the author's style was reflected in the translation.

Original: U qirq-qirq besh yoshlar chamasidagi qorachadan kelgan, xushqomad qalam qosh bir xotin edi. [6, 4]

Translation: She was forty or forty-five years old. She was a beautiful woman. [7, 6]

In the text, the words *hushkomad* and *kalamkosh*, which served to create artistry, are expressed by the generic word *beautiful*. In our opinion, it would be better if the translation was as follows:

Translation: She was a pretty, slender woman around 40.

In conclusion, in the stories that we have analyzed, artistry and style are expressed in their own way. In their translations, the artistry of the original and the artist's style are recreated to some extent. In fact, not all the image tools that created artistry and creative style were reflected. Variations in turns, especially word choice, have been significantly explored; while working with meanings in translations, special attention was paid to the problems of which of them are transferred from the source language to the translation language, and which of them are not transferred to another language. Both of our translators understood that the novels fully describe the national traditions of the Uzbek people, the hardships and injustices the people experienced at that time, and tried to convey them to the reader in the translations.

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